

“I See You Baby, Shakin’ That Ass”: User Perceptions of Unintentional Anthropomorphism and Zoomorphism in Consumer Products

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Abstract

Anecdotal evidence suggests, independently of any intentional use of human and animal visual references in the development of product detail, that many people respond to unintentional references, even treating products as people or animals, developing likes and dislikes that can be described in terms of the products’ ‘personalities’ or ‘characters’.

This paper describes a series of pilot experiments devised to be an objective examination of anecdotal evidence. They measured the extent to which respondents perceived animal and human physical features in everyday products, and the extent to which these perceptions correlated with positive and negative connotations. A total of 48 respondents were shown photographs of commonplace consumer products (kettles, shavers, vacuum cleaners, toasters, radios), and asked to rate them in terms of perceived anthropomorphic and zoomorphic (A & Z) references, and in terms of perceived abstract qualities (boring/exciting, hostile/friendly, happy/sad, uptight/carefree). A high degree of correlation was found between positive abstract qualities and greater perception of A & Z references.

Further work utilized image morphing software to measure respondents’ preferences for finely differentiated modifications of visual detail of similar products, showing that subtle A & Z references were preferred over explicit parody.

Results suggest that the most effective use of A & Z references for embedding brand values is when they are barely perceived – they become evident when attention is drawn to them, but unnoticed by many consumers who may nevertheless be unconsciously attracted by the abstract qualities with which they are associated. There is the opportunity for designers to take the lead in embedding the visual triggers that tend to be discovered and activated in advertising campaigns such as Renault’s Megane television advertisement to the theme of Groove Armada’s ‘I see you baby (shakin’ that ass)’, which features the car’s hind quarters as expressive of a personality and attitude.

Keywords: unintentional, anthropomorphism, zoomorphism, abstract qualities, experiments

Introduction

Whilst there is a widespread assumption in design education and practice that the designer is the prime agent for imbuing products with the values perceived by the end user, perspectives from other disciplines suggest that values are ascribed to products at many different stages of their lives, and at the instigation of agents other than designers. For example, it is not uncommon for product qualities to be highlighted in advertising campaigns and for those

qualities to have been recognized in marketing departments rather than in design studios, particularly in the case of subtle references.

However, what little evidence exists of the sequence of events in the establishment of product character tends to be anecdotal, based on the recollection of those who may have an interest in reinforcing what has become a shared perception. Commentators and critics may be the source of nicknames that recognize anthropomorphic and zoomorphic (A&Z) references, as in the case of the ‘frog-eyed’ Austin Healey Sprite motor car of the late 1950s. A television advertising campaign for the Renault Megane (launched 2003) utilizes rapid cuts between images of the hips and buttocks of men and women (but mostly women) both at rest and in motion, inter-cut with glimpses of the car’s rear. To further emphasize the anthropomorphic references, the images are accompanied by an audio track taken from a re-mix of Groove Armada’s ‘I see you baby (shakin’ that ass)’. The intention of the visual references, and the accompanying music, in its lyrics, their delivery and the musical editing, is to express an attitude. The car is presented as young, sassy, more female than male, active and carefree.

The anthropomorphic references, then, are determined as much by aspects of the self image of its intended purchasers as by the designers’ reasons for form development. There is always a formal agenda that contributes to the brand identity of a range of products, and other cars in the current Renault range (Vel Satis, Scenic, Espace) share detail features of an emphasized rear. However, their advertising, aimed at different market groups, eschews anthropomorphism for other value references. Car designers have long paid attention to a car’s ‘stance’, as expressive of an attitude, usually described in comparatively simple terms such as ‘aggressive’, ‘confident’, ‘assertive’ or some such, and the Megane campaign is natural extension of this focus on attitude.

Whatever the agency that encourages the sharing of A&Z perceptions, the ability to recognize A&Z characteristics in inanimate objects is widespread. In particular, our ability to perceive facial features is well documented.

Frisby (1979) suggests that our brains store structural and symbolic information and that when we look at things this information is activated. This suggests that the brain has a classification system for common structures such as faces, and for the range of emotions and

behaviors provoked by facial expressions. Our brains contain cells that respond selectively to the sight of biologically important objects such as faces and hands (Perret et al, 1995).

We fixate on faces from a very young age. Fantz's experiments (Gregory 1966) describe how infants, when shown a selection of patterned circles, fixated for longer on the circle that resembled a human face. As well as an inbuilt ability to recognize facial characteristics, we also tend to ascribe emotions and characteristics to objects from an early age (Vernon 1963). Vernon documented this process, noting how children gave characteristics, such as 'mean' or 'soft', to numbers they were presented with. Feelings and actions were also attributed to objects, as when a child referred to a broken biscuit as 'poor biscuit'. These emotional characteristics were more important to the children than was the shape itself.

Anecdotal evidence suggests that perceiving A&Z references in objects is often a case of seeing something that has not been put there intentionally by the designer. Gregory (1966) says that we use past experience to augment sensory information. Perception is a matter of suggesting and testing until we find the best 'fit' or hypothesis for what we are seeing. This process becomes confused when we can see two separate forms in one object. Many visual illusions work in this manner. The Necker cube is one example (Gregory 1966). It is a simple illusion: a line drawing of a cube, with a small circle drawn on one side. The brain cannot decide whether the circle is sitting on the front or back panel of the cube. The brain tries to fit the correct hypothesis to the cube, but perception continually changes; neither hypothesis is allowed to stay, as neither one is a better fit than the other. Is our perception of human and animal shapes in objects a case of our brain attempting to find the correct hypothesis? Once seen, anecdotal evidence suggests that it is very hard to 'unsee', for example, a 'face' in a product. Our brain identifies a familiar pattern and ascribes meaning to it, which we cannot then disregard.

Whilst designers are preoccupied with visual manifestations of A&Z characteristics, non-visual anthropomorphic and zoomorphic models have been used in other disciplines that address product issues. Nieminen-Sundell and Pantzar (2003) describe the evolution of products in terms of the ecology of the forest, including predator-prey relationships of competing household products.

This project was devised to develop methodologies for providing experimental evidence of some of the anthropomorphic and zoomorphic issues that rely heavily on anecdotal evidence. Are human and animal features things that people will always see, even in products that have no intentional features of that kind? Bush (1990) carried out research that indicated that recognition of human and animal features in products is fundamental to our perception of the world around us - a way of understanding our role in the inanimate, physical world. He concluded that people would always see some human or animal features in a product, even if this were not the deliberate, conscious decision of the designer. If this is the case, then a designer should have some understanding of how we respond to, and how much we feel comfortable with, a product containing these references.

Do people like to see human or animal features in products? This question underpins much of the reasoning for the project. Our habit of perceiving the world around us in terms of our own bodies perhaps helps us to form links with inanimate and machine-like things, to lessen the barriers between ourselves and all the artefacts we produce and surround ourselves with. The issue of gender encroaches on this.

The work of Howell (1999) showed that form was as important as colour, if not more, when deciding the 'gender appropriateness' of a product. The received wisdom in marketing is that 'female' products tend to contain more rounded, organic forms, and 'male' ones more mechanical angular shapes. This stereotyping of gender-appropriate shapes may affect the popularity, gender-wise, of products that contain obvious human or animal shapes and features.

Figure 1, Radio designed by George Sowden. Its round form and small ear-like protuberances offer non-threatening imagery to the viewer. In tests (described below) this product was rated the most 'friendly' of its product group.

Project Aims

- To create methodologies for providing experimental evidence for A&Z issues that currently rely heavily on anecdotal evidence.
- To discover whether people attribute more positive emotional abstract values to products that are perceived to have stronger human or animal visual references.
- To show that, if people really do perceive products with human and animal features in a more positive way, it should therefore be possible to control this emotional reaction, using anthropomorphism as a design tool.

Test 1: Testing for Emotional Responses to Products

The tests were designed to cover a number of areas:

- Does our liking of a product correlate to the strength of anthropomorphic and zoomorphic recognition?
- Will people see anthropomorphic or zoomorphic features in products that are chosen specifically not to contain obvious references?
- To what extent will people attribute personality to a product? Will this correlate in any way to the strength of animal or human visual cues?

Test structure

The tests consisted of two A2 picture boards upon which subjects were asked to rank products. This was followed by a questionnaire.

Picture boards

Each picture board test used five different types of everyday small electrical products: kettles, toasters, shavers, radios and vacuum cleaners. Each of these product types was represented by a range of five individual products, chosen as a representative sample of current designs, encompassing both products with an obvious machine aesthetic and those with a highly organic aesthetic.

Figure 2, The range of electric jug kettles used in test 1.

Figure 3, The range of electric shavers used in test 1.

Test subjects were asked to place the pictures of products on a numbered matrix, in which ratings of 0-5 represented a low-high rating of two criteria:

- Visual appeal
- Strength of human or animal visual references

The picture board questions were presented in the order reported to avoid the subjects consciously considering the anthropomorphic or zoomorphic qualities while they judged how much they liked the products.

Figure 4, The test board, showing the full range of products used in test 1.

Questionnaire

Next, each subject was given a questionnaire sheet. Subjects were asked to attribute personality traits to each product using pairs of semantic differentials. These differentials formed the pole points on a seven-point scale, the middle value of which was 'neutral'. After this the subject was asked to circle supplied words that best describe the human or animal features they had seen, and provide an alternative word if preferred.

	Very		Neutral			Very		
	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	
Hostile								Friendly
Boring								Exciting
Uptight								Carefree
Sad								Happy

Figure 5. The pairs of semantic differentials used in the test 1 questionnaire.

Bar charts were compiled to show the amount by which each product was judged to have each characteristic. Each characteristic could be ascribed on 3 levels: 3 (very), 2 (moderately), 1 (a little). Each score on the three levels was counted and added together to produce three overall amounts. In this way the relative popularity of each product could be judged.

This method also made it possible to see to what extent each characteristic was ascribed to each product.

Analysis of Test 1 Results

48 people took part in the tests, 27 of which were designers or design students. The remaining subjects had no training in design. 22 of the subjects were female, and 26 male.

Using the 0-5 scales for both of these criteria means that the scores can easily be compared to each other. The corresponding bar chart (Figure 6) show that the more organically-shaped the kettles, the stronger the positive attributes perceived by the test subjects.

The test results show that the subjects identified those products that were chosen because of their organic features. They also found it easy to find animal and human features in the more neutral products. Those products that had been included to represent an obvious machine aesthetic scored lowest on A&Z recognition in the test, but still recorded some recognition.

There was a strong correlation between those products that scored highly on strength of A&Z references, and those that were thought to possess positive personality traits (see Figures 6 and 7). These results also correlated with the degree to which the test subjects found the product visually appealing (Figures 6 and 7).

It appeared that the products that scored highest on 'visual appeal' were those products with subtle A&Z features, rather than those with obvious ones. These also score highly on the attribution of positive personality traits. This tentative finding was explored in a further series of experiments (Test 2, see below).

Examples of test results (Test 1)

The results are for two exemplar product categories: electric shavers, and electric jug kettles.

Figure 6, Results for the kettles product range. The bar chart shows the degree to which each product was liked, next to the degree to which it was perceived to have A&Z references.

Figure 7, Results for the shaver product range. The bar chart shows the degree to which each product was liked, next to the degree to which it was perceived to have A&Z references.

Test 2: Differentiating Positive and Negative Reactions

It was surmised that it might be possible to identify the point at which human and animal references make people feel better about a product. By using data already collected during Phase One, it was possible to identify those products that attracted the most negative and positive personality attributes. These products could be used as pole points on a 'morphic' scale. The images of these products are then 'morphed' between the perceived positive and negative 'morphic poles', using proprietary 2-D morphing software. (Figure 8)

Shaver and Kettles Morph Series

The diagrams below show the entire 'morph' series for the two chosen products, electric shavers and kettles. The product images that form the two 'morphic poles' are the least and most popular products identified from their product groups in test 2. The products between these two poles show the 'morphing' process from one product to the other.

Figure 8, The range of morphed products.

Having created a series of 'morph' stages from one 'morphic pole' to another, these images were presented to test subjects, to determine at which point the disliked product becomes liked. From this we can judge what levels of perceived human/animal features are needed to create a positive perception of a product.

Structure of Test 2

The test subject is shown the morph series, in the form of individual pictures mounted on foam board. They are then asked to divide the products into two groups. If further prompting is needed, they are told to group together products that look similar to one another.

Figure 9, Test subject dividing the products into two groups.

Once this task had been completed the subject was then asked to choose from each group their favourite and least favourite product. To correlate with the positive and negative 'morphic poles' identified in test 1, they should then choose the two original products as their most and least favourite, with the other two products being variations of the two 'morphed' products.

Figure 10, A typical grouping of the 8 'morph' stages. The subject was asked to place their favourite products from each group on the top row, and their least favourites on the bottom.

Outcomes of Test 2

16 subjects took part in the test: 7 females and 9 males.

Figure 11, The results of the Shaver morph series tests. Scores are the aggregate of the number of subjects choosing shaver as favourite and the number choosing shaver as least favourite (number of test subjects = 16).

Figure 12, The results of the Kettles morph series tests. Scores are the aggregate of the number of subjects choosing kettle as favourite and the number choosing kettle as least favourite (number of test subjects = 16).

Analysis of Test Results

It was possible for subjects to determine the point on the 'morphic scale' at which one product became the other; at which the non-organic became positively organic/anthropomorphic.

When dividing the 'morph' series into two sections, 70% of the test subjects put the products into the same categories. This shows a general agreement among the subjects about the point at which one 'pole' becomes the other.

This is useful as, in this particular case, it helps to determine the level of human or animal features a non-organic product may need in order to soften people's (often negative) reaction to the product. The change in the product was from a non-organic product (rectangular, geometrical) to an organic product (curvaceous, with head/body divide). Fig. 13 shows how

the subjects were able to identify the point at which the product crossed the dividing line between these two states.

Figure 13, Diagram showing product groupings for morphed products.

This points to a way of instilling abstract values into a product. It is not being suggested that products should be morphed into one another, but it does imply that relatively small changes need to take place: subtle differences that alter people's perception in a positive way.

Figures 11 and 12 suggest that there is a general tendency for the test subject to pick the morphic pole products as their least favourites. These results need to be considered alongside those from test 1, in which subjects expressed a preference for products at the positive morphic scale. One explanation is that the 'morph' tests offer a greater degree of fine detail differentiation than in the earlier tests, and that subjects have responded by giving more careful consideration of these distinctions than were possible in the comparatively more limited choices of test 1. In figures 11 and 12 we can see that in both series', the predominant favourite product came from around the middle of the morphic scale.

A possible explanation is that it is the subtle changes that are enhancing the popularity of the product. These changes can make an unpopular product more popular, but they appear to make the most popular product less so, as the test subjects tended to pick a less organic/anthropomorphic product as their favourite.

These test results were divided into answers given by men and answers given by women. The popularity of the middle products may be partly explained by a generalisation of stereotypically male or female features: e.g. rounded shapes versus angular. This would make

the product more acceptable to both male and female. However, the gender issue is not of primary importance here.

Howell (1999) notes that by removing the gendered colour bias, it was revealed that form played a major part in determining the gender of a product. In her tests, pictures were printed in black and white to remove gendered colour bias.

Conclusions

The project tested methodologies for measuring perceptions of A&Z references: it is possible to test in a systematic way for intangible qualities and for those things generally perceived as more frivolous aspects of products.

The test subjects found human and animal features in many of the products, not just those that had obvious A&Z features. This upholds part of the original hypothesis, which was that people would always see A&Z references in products, something that Bush postulated. It was found to be much harder to predict exactly what kinds of A&Z references people would see, as the subjects often saw very different traits in the same object, especially in the case of more neutral products.

The results confirm other points of the original research; that people can and do apply abstract emotional values to products. Further, these abstract values are separate from other notions of product value. These emotional responses are based on conscious or unconscious perception of anthropomorphic or zoomorphic forms. The test results indicate that the subjects perceived products that contained elements of human and/or animal features in a more positive way. Products that used overt human or animal imagery were less popular than those that used subtle hints of such features. A subsequent finding was that these subtle forms still tended to elicit positive emotional responses from the test subjects.

As the experiments show, it is very difficult to fully remove the visual cues from a product that trigger human or animal recognition. Even small nuances can trigger this sort of recognition. This recognition, coupled with the emotional responses that it generates can be manipulated by designers to create products that generate emotional responses. The second set of tests demonstrated that people can be made to feel better about a product that they have

attributed negative characteristics to. A morphing program allows a series of similar product images to be generated, that can then be used for consumer testing. With further development, this process may become a New Product Development tool, that would let designers control the embedding of the visual triggers that tend to be discovered and activated in advertising. This may help to determine the level of human or animal features a non-organic product may need in order to soften people's (often negative) reaction to the product.

An interesting observation that arose from the project is that the recognition of human and animal features is often occasioned by product details and their placement. The designer can control these factors, or their placement can, more commonly, be influenced by manufacturing and production requirements, eg, the fixings and details required for manufacture and/or assembly. If this is the case, then a designer should have some understanding of how we respond to, and how much we feel comfortable with, a product containing A&Z references. The project provides some methodologies that give the perception of A&Z forms some experimental basis, and that have the potential to be developed into a practical design tool.

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